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Compact circular-patch-based bandpass filter for ultra-wideband wireless communication systems

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Abstract

Ultra-wideband (UWB) is a radio technology that enables low-power-level, short-range, and wide-bandwidth communication, and it has been widely applied in personal area networks, precision geolocation, medical, surveillance, and vehicular radar systems. Since Federal Communications Commission released the unlicensed use of the UWB range (3.1–10.6 GHz), a significant attention has been paid to the development of UWB devices, particularly UWB bandpass filters. In this paper, we propose a novel UWB bandpass filter based on circular patch resonator that is grounded by via and perturbed by slits and defected ground structures. The resonator's behaviour is analysed in detail and it is shown that its specific configuration allows a flexible control of the three lowest resonant modes, which are used to form UWB passband. To demonstrate the potential of the resonator, a UWB filter has been designed, fabricated, and measured. The filter is characterized by the insertion loss lower than 1 dB and return loss higher than 17 dB within the passband, as well as by very small group delay variation of only 0.07 ns. Also, the filter exhibits suppression higher than 19 dB up to 30 GHz, and very small overall dimensions of only $0.31\lambda_g \times 0.31\lambda_g$, and thus it outperforms other published UWB filters.

Keywords

Ultra-wideband; patch resonator; bandpass filter; defected ground structure

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1. Introduction

Ultra-wideband (UWB) represents a radio technology that enables low-power-level, short-range, and wide-bandwidth communication over a large portion of the radio spectrum. This technology was first adopted by the US Federal Communication Commission (FCC) covering the range from 3.1 to 10.6 GHz, and it has found a number of applications including personal area networks, precision geolocation systems, wall and through-wall imaging systems, medical, surveillance, and vehicular radar systems [1]. Due to the low-power-level operation and the usage of very narrow or short duration pulses, UWB provides coexistence with current narrowband and wideband services, large channel capacity, low signal-to-noise ratio, resistance to jamming, and high performance in multipath channels.

Inevitable components of every UWB device are UWB bandpass filters, which are required to exhibit low loss, high selectivity, small group delay variation, wide upper stopband, and small overall size. Since these requirements are mutually opposed, the design of a UWB filter is a rather challenging task, and therefore different methods and technologies have been employed to address it. Whilst there have been proposed only few filters based on waveguide and substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) technologies [2-4], microstrip technology has been widely used. This is primarily due to the fact that microstrip technology allows integration as well as significant size reduction and design flexibility in comparison to the previous two. At the same time, it has sufficient power-handling capabilities due to the low-power UWB standards.

Majority of microstrip UWB filters are based on multimode resonators [5-12], however there are also configurations based on short-circuited stubs [13-15], parallel-coupled lines [16-18],

patch resonators [19], multi-layer structures [20-23], composite right-/left-handed unit cells [24-25], composition of bandstop and bandpass filters [26], and coplanar waveguide structures [27]. Although most proposed filters exhibit good in-band performance and selectivity, they typically fail to simultaneously address other key requirements, in particular small group delay variation, wide upper stopband, and small size.

In this paper, we propose an UWB filter which practically reconciles and addresses all abovementioned requirements. It is based on grounded circular patch resonator perturbed with slits and defected ground structures (DGS), whose three lowest fundamental modes - TM_{100}^z , TM_{110}^z , and TM_{210}^z , are used to form the ultra-wide passband. The grounding via is introduced into the patch to position the so-called zero mode TM_{100}^z at a non-zero frequency. As effective mechanisms to control the modes of a resonant structure [28-29], slits and DGS are used to reduce the resonant frequencies of TM_{110}^z and TM_{210}^z modes and to obtain a spectral distribution of the three modes that is appropriate for UWB operation. Consequently, the perturbations enable significant miniaturization of the structure.

The proposed patch resonator is analysed in detail and the UWB filter design procedure is given. The filter has been fabricated and the measurement results show a good agreement with the simulated ones. The filter is characterized by small insertion loss of 1 dB, good selectivity, very small group delay variation of only 0.07 ns, suppression higher than 19 dB up to 30 GHz, and small overall size of $0.31\lambda_g \times 0.31\lambda_g$, where λ_g represents the guided wavelength at the central frequency.

2. Grounded circular patch resonator perturbed with slits and DGS

Conventional circular patch resonator can be considered as a cavity resonator whose lateral sides represent magnetic walls, and its top and bottom sides electric walls [30]. Such structure supports only transversal magnetic (TM) resonant modes, and their resonant frequencies are calculated using the following expressions:

$$f_{nm} = \frac{cK_{nm}}{2\pi a_e \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}, \quad (1)$$

$$K_{n1} = \begin{cases} 3.83171, & n = 0 \\ 1.84118, & n = 1 \\ 3.05424, & n = 2 \\ 4.20119, & n = 3 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$a_e = a \sqrt{1 + \frac{2h}{\pi a} \left[\ln \frac{\pi a}{2h} + 1.7726 \right]}, \quad (3)$$

where K_{nm} represents the root of the Bessel function derivative, ϵ_r is dielectric constant of the substrate, whilst c stands for the light speed in vacuum. The parameter a_e stands for the effective patch radius, a is the radius of the patch, and h is the height of the substrate.

Figure 1: Electric field and current distribution of three lowest resonant modes of conventional circular patch. (a) TM^z_{100} . (b) TM^z_{110} . (c) TM^z_{210} .

Figure 1 shows the electric field and current distributions for three lowest modes of the conventional circular patch - TM_{100}^z , TM_{110}^z , and TM_{210}^z . TM_{100}^z mode presents the so-called zero or DC mode whose resonant frequency is equal to zero. However, if a grounding via is introduced into the conventional patch structure, the TM_{100}^z resonance is shifted from zero to a non-zero frequency, which is positioned below the resonant frequency of the TM_{110}^z mode. The effect of the via can be understood as introducing a series inductance to the LC -resonance circuit that describes the lowest non-zero resonance of the unloaded patch - TM_{110}^z , where C is the static capacitance of the patch configuration. As a consequence, a resonant circuit with a non-zero resonant frequency positioned below that of the TM_{110}^z is created, and it corresponds to the TM_{100}^z mode [31].

This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the response of the conventional patch and the response of a patch grounded by centrally positioned via. The patches are realized on Rogers R04003C substrate of height $h = 0.51$ mm, copper thickness $t = 0.0175$ mm, permittivity $\epsilon_r = 3.38$ and losses $\tan\delta = 0.0025$, and their diameters are equal to 8.2 mm, whilst the via diameter is equal to 0.5 mm.

Figure 2: Comparison of the responses of conventional and grounded patch resonator.

Figure 3: Electric field and current distribution of three lowest resonant modes of grounded circular patch. (a) TM^z_{100} . (b) TM^z_{110} . (c) TM^z_{210} .

Figure 3 shows the electric field and current distribution of the three modes of the grounded patch, which confirm the previous statement. Namely, the lowest mode resembles the TM^z_{100} electric field distribution of the non-grounded patch in Figure 1, i.e. it is almost uniform over the cavity except for the position of the via, at which the field vanishes due to boundary conditions. Also, the two higher modes are practically the same as the corresponding ones in Figure 1.

The conventional patch resonator exhibits two resonances at 11.8 GHz and 18.8 GHz, which correspond to the TM^z_{110} and TM^z_{210} modes, respectively. Besides these two resonances, the grounded counterpart exhibits an additional resonance positioned below them, 6 GHz, and it corresponds to the TM^z_{100} mode. It should be noted that the introduction of the via practically does not influence the spectral positions of the TM^z_{110} and TM^z_{210} modes.

Occurrence of TM^z_{100} resonant mode at non-zero frequency due to shorting via, opens up a possibility of utilization of circular patch resonator for UWB filtering operation. Namely, TM^z_{100} resonant mode, together with TM^z_{110} and TM^z_{210} modes, can be used to form an ultra-

wide passband. To realize the UWB filter with excellent in-band performance, the three modes should be evenly distributed within the passband 3.1-10.6 GHz, i.e. ideally at the frequencies of 4.98, 6.85, and 8.75 GHz. We note that these values represent ideal ones, not readily achievable, and the deviations of 10% from the ideal values are acceptable since UWB filter response is not extremely sensitive to them.

Figure 2 shows that the resonant frequencies are very distantly positioned, i.e. only the first resonance is positioned approximately at the desired frequency, whilst the two higher modes are positioned practically out of the UWB frequency range. The simplest method to shift TM_{110}^z and TM_{210}^z resonances within UWB range is to enlarge the patch structure, however, that would result in unacceptably large circuit.

To achieve TM_{110}^z and TM_{210}^z resonant frequencies reduction, whilst preserving the size of the circuit, the following concept has been applied. It has been shown that introduction of the perturbations such as slits and defected ground structures (DGS) into a resonant structure, can significantly change the characteristics of the microstrip resonators in terms of their resonant frequencies [28-29].

Namely, DGS are perturbations realized in the ground layer which affects effective capacitance and inductance of the resonators, and thus their modes' distribution and resonant frequencies. More concrete, DGS perturbs the current distribution in the ground plane modifying the equivalent parameters over the defected region, and thus influences resonant modes characteristics, which provides reduction of resonant frequency, i.e. resonator miniaturization. The strongest influence on resonators' characteristics is achieved if DGS are positioned below the resonator's areas with strong current distribution. Larger DGS slots provide more significant influence on resonant modes and more significant circuit size reduction.

Similarly, slits that are made directly in a patch structure affect the current distribution in the top layer, i.e. the slits extend the current path of a resonant mode and in that manner decrease the corresponding resonant frequency, thus providing circuit size reduction. Certainly, the slits are most effective when they are positioned in the area of a strong current distribution.

To achieve the control of both TM_{110}^z and TM_{210}^z modes, DGS and slits have been introduced in the grounded patch structure. Figure 3 shows that area of the highest current density for TM_{110}^z mode is positioned at the central part of the patch, whilst highest current density of TM_{210}^z mode is achieved at the outer parts of the resonator. Therefore, the slits in the form of straight lines and DGS in the form of two semicircles have been introduced as shown in Figure 4. In that manner, DGS are expected to predominantly affect the TM_{110}^z mode, and the slits TM_{210}^z mode.

The influence of the slits and DGS are illustrated in Figures 5 and 6, respectively, where the responses for different values of the corresponding geometrical parameters C_1 and D_1 are shown. In the case when the slits' length is varied, the slits' width and DGS radius are fixed to 0.4 and 2.15 mm, respectively. On the other hand, DGS radius is varied for the fixed slits' length of 2.8 mm. In all cases, the diameter of the patch and the grounding via are equal to 8.2 and 0.4 mm, respectively, whilst the parameter C_2 is equal to 0.5 mm.

Figure 4: Grounded circular patch resonator with perturbations. (a) Slits in top conductive layer. (b) Defected ground structures in ground layer.

It can be seen that the slits' length affects all three modes of interest. However, one should note that the TM_{210}^z mode is the most affected one, since the length variation from 0 to 2.8 mm provides almost 50% resonant frequency reduction. The TM_{100}^z and TM_{110}^z modes are less affected, and the influence of the slits becomes pronounced when the length achieve the larger values. In that case, the slits are closely positioned to the via and they overlap DGS, which means that the slits reach the areas of the strong currents of the TM_{100}^z and TM_{110}^z modes, and thus disturb them.

Figure 5: Responses of the grounded patch resonator with slits and DGS for different values of the slits' length D_l .

Figure 6: Responses of the grounded patch resonator with slits and DGS for different values of the DGS radius C_l .

As expected, the DGS perturbations strongly affect TM_{110}^z mode, whilst the other two modes practically remain unaffected. Only when the implemented DGS are large enough to reach outer parts of patch, they slightly disturb the current path of TM_{210}^z mode and lower its resonant frequency.

To provide a comprehensive analysis of the structure, Figure 7 shows how the via diameter influences the resonant frequencies of the three modes. Since the diameter is inversely proportional to the via inductance, the increase of the via diameter causes the increase of the TM_{100}^z resonant frequency and vice versa. Positioned in the centre of the patch and closely to the DGS, the via also affects the TM_{110}^z mode, whilst it does not have any effect on the mode TM_{210}^z .

Besides the three modes that are to be used for the UWB filter, the higher-order modes are also a matter of interest since their spectral position and strength determine the width of the upper stopband. Namely, another reason for large DGS and slits is the fact that such

Figure 7: Responses of the grounded patch resonator with slits and DGS for different values of the via diameter A .

perturbations are not favourable for higher-order mode fields' configurations and thus they significantly weaken and suppress the higher-order modes.

Figure 8 shows the patch response in the range from 10 to 30 GHz for different values of the parameters C_I and D_I . The first higher-order mode TM_{310}^z , which appears around 19 GHz, is strongly suppressed primarily due to the slits. Namely, the slits are positioned in the area of high electrical field intensity of the mode TM_{310}^z and thus they deteriorate the mode intensity, which is further supported by the presence of DGS. For the reasonable values of the slits' length, the mode can be suppressed even below 20 dB. Moreover, other higher-order modes appearing in the range 24-30 GHz are also suppressed below 20 dB, however primarily due to the presence of DGS.

The previous analysis has shown that the proposed structure offers a straightforward control of the modes and thus significant design freedom in their spectral positioning. Although the slits affect all three modes, the DGS and via have been shown to be control mechanisms that can compensate this, since they affect only two or even only one mode of interest. Therefore, the proposed configuration is an excellent candidate for the UWB filter.

Figure 8: Influence of the parameters C_I and D_I on the higher-order modes: (a) Influence of C_I with fixed value of $D_I=2.8$ mm. (b) Influence of D_I with fixed $C_I=2.15$ mm.

3. UWB filter design and results

To demonstrate the potential of the grounded circular patch with slits and DGS, we have designed an UWB filter using the following procedure. The first step is to determine the diameter of the circular patch and to that end we rely on the analysis from the previous section. Namely, it was shown that the slits can be used to reduce the third resonant frequency by around 50%. Also, the slits are only mechanism to control the third mode, which means that the appropriate positioning of the third mode within the UWB passband, should be the step to follow the diameter determination. If it were otherwise, the filter design procedure would include multiple optimization steps. Therefore, the diameter of the patch is determined using the expressions (1)-(3) to provide TM_{210}^z resonant frequency to be approximately twice as higher than the ideal position of the third mode, previously explained to be 8.75 GHz. Taking into consideration the previous statements, the following design step is to introduce the slits and optimize their length to appropriately position the third mode within the UWB band.

Afterwards, the patch is grounded by a via and its diameter is varied to achieve the first resonant mode to be positioned around 5 GHz. Since the DGS practically affects only the second mode, in the pre-final step, two DGS semicircles are introduced and their radius optimized to position the second mode around 6.85 GHz.

The final step includes inductive coupling of the patch to the feeding lines, which however slightly deteriorates the modes' positions. To compensate for that and to achieve proper impedance matching and excellent overall response of the filter, the taper lines as well as the geometrical parameters A , C_l , and D_l , are finely tuned. For the same reason, the slits have been somewhat expanded towards the patch edge and accordingly optimized.

The final layout of the filter is shown in Figure 9, and the corresponding geometrical parameters are as follows: $A=0.35$ mm, $C_1=2.3$ mm, $C_2=0.5$ mm, $D_1=2.8$ mm, $D_2=0.4$ mm, $D_3=1$ mm, $D_4=0.5$ mm, $R=8.1$ mm, $W_T=0.7$ mm. The designed UWB filter has been fabricated using standard PCB technology and the photograph of the fabricated circuit is shown in Fig 10.

The simulated and measured S -parameters and group delay variations in the passband are compared in Figures 11 and 12, respectively. They show very good agreement except for a small spectral shift and slightly increased losses in the passband which is due to the manufacturer's tolerance on dielectric constant and the losses introduced by the end launch SMA connectors.

Figure 9: The layout of the proposed UWB bandpass filter.

Figure 10: Photograph of the fabricated UWB bandpass filter.

Figure 11: Simulated and measured S -parameters of UWB bandpass filter.

Figure 12: Simulated and measured group delay variation of UWB bandpass filter.

The measured passband ranges from 3.07 to 10.51 GHz, the insertion loss (IL) is lower than 1 dB and return loss (RL) higher than 17 dB within the passband. The proposed UWB filter is characterized by very small group delay variation of only 0.07 ns. At the same time, the filter exhibits good selectivity and suppression higher than 19 dB up to 30 GHz. Although the resonance that corresponds to the higher-order resonant mode TM_{310}^z , can be observed around 19

GHz, it is strongly suppressed, and this is primarily due to large DGS and slits perturbation, which significantly weaken the higher-order modes. Moreover, the filter has very small overall dimensions of only $0.31\lambda_g \times 0.31\lambda_g$.

Table 1: Comparison with published UWB bandpass filters.

	RL (dB)	IL (dB)	GDV (ns)	Size ($\lambda_g \times \lambda_g$)	USW [dB (GHz-GHz)]
[5]	>15	<1.1	0.33	0.58x0.43	>15(13-30)
[6]	>10	n/a	0.3	0.82x0.16	>20(12.1-25.5)
[7]	>12.5	<2	0.28	0.575x0.4	>22.5(11.3-18)
[8]	>11.1	<1.4	0.29	0.74x0.54	>20(11.3-29.7)
[9]	>17	<0.7	0.5	0.62x0.15	>15(11.5-17)
[10]	>10.6	<1.3	1.76	0.89x0.21	n/a
[11]	>12.8	<0.9	0.4	0.36x0.36	n/a
[12]	>17.5	<0.25	0.3	0.71x0.31	>20(11-17.4)
[13]	>12	<1	0.4	0.7x0.4	>30(11-20)
[14]	>14	<0.86	0.15	0.77x0.35	>16(13-30)
[15]	>17	<0.6	n/a	0.57x0.40	>30(12.5-40)
[16]	>18	<1	0.12	0.71x0.1	>30(12-24)
[17]	>15	<3	n/a	0.59x0.44	>10(10.6-12.5)
[18]	>16	<0.8	0.2	0.24x0.19	>20(10.9-25.1)
[19]	>17	<0.9	0.25	0.26x0.26	>11(12.8-15)
[20]	>11.6	<1.43	0.58	0.26x0.28	>20.9(11.3-20)
[21]	>10	0.35	0.45	0.87x0.36	>38.8(10.6-18)
[22]	>10	0.5	0.2	0.35x0.33	>25(10.8-18)
[23]	>10.8	<1.06	0.45	1.02x0.68	>20(11-14)
[24]	>11	<0.5	0.4	0.52x0.15	>18(10.6-16)
[25]	>12.5	<2.1	0.26	0.70x0.25	>20(12-14)
[26]	>15	<1	0.1	1.75x0.44	>23.8(12.6-26.9)
[27]	>15	<1	n/a	1x0.20	n/a
This work	>17	<1	0.07	0.31x0.31	>19(13.1-30)

Table 1 compares the proposed filter and the previously reported microstrip UWB filters, where λ_g denotes guided wavelength at the central frequency, GDV group delay variation, and USW upper stopband width. The proposed filter has comparable or better in-band performance in comparison to others, and it is characterized by very compact size, a wide upper stopband, and the smallest group delay variation. Although the filters presented in [9], [16], [18], [19], [20], and [24] have smaller dimensions, they have significantly higher GDV and narrower upper stopbands. On the other hand, the filter in [15] has wider upper stopband, however it is characterized by a large circuit area. To conclude, the proposed filter simultaneously addresses all major requirements for UWB filters, and thus outperforms other published filters and represents an excellent candidate for applications in UWB devices.

4. Conclusion

We proposed an ultra-wideband bandpass filter that is based on a grounded circular patch resonator perturbed with slits and defected ground structures. The resonator's behaviour has been analysed in detail and it was shown that it offers a significant design freedom for UWB applications. To demonstrate the potential of the resonator, an UWB filter has been designed, fabricated, and measured. The simulated and measured results are in good agreement, and the filter is characterized by the insertion loss lower than 1 dB and return loss higher than 17 dB within the passband, as well as by very small group delay variation of only 0.07 ns. Also, the filter exhibits suppression higher than 19 dB up to 30 GHz, and very small overall dimensions of only $0.31\lambda_g \times 0.31\lambda_g$. Taking into consideration its overall performance, the proposed filter meet all imposed requirements and outperforms other published UWB configurations.

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